

REAL TIME LOGO RECOGNITION USING YOLOV2 ON ANDROID

Primbetov Abbaz, Computer Engineering, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences.

Computer Science, College of Information Science and Engineering, Hunan University, Changsha, China

Primbetov Aziz, Information Technologies, Computer Engineering, Tashkent University of Information Technology Nukus Branch

Normuminov Anvarjon, Computer Engineering, University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences.

Email: abbaz0203@mail.ru

Saparboev Jamoladdin

ANNOTATION

The goal of this project is to implement an object detection model suitable in terms of size and speed to run on an Android device and detect logos in real-time. The proposed approach is based on YOLOv2 (You Only Look Once) state-of-the-art, real-time object detection for logos and this project used the FlickrLogos-32 dataset. The experimental results show that we obtained a final accuracy of 82.3% and a speed of 35 fps (frames per second) on the NVidia GeForce GTX 1070.

Key words: Object detection, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), You Only Look Once (YOLO), Faster R-CNN (Region-based Convolutional Neural Networks).

Introduction

A logo usually has a recognizable and distinctive graphic design, stylized name or unique symbol for identifying an organization. It is affixed, included, or printed on all advertising, buildings, communications, literature, products, stationery, vehicles, etc. During recent years, deep learning methods have shown to be effective for image classification, localization and detection. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) [3–5] are used to extract information from images and are the main element of modern deep learning and computer vision methods.

Problem Formulation

A logo can be thought of as an artistic expression of a brand, it can be either a (stylized) letter or text, a graphical figure or any combination of these. Furthermore, some logos have a fixed set of colors with known fonts while others vary a lot in color and specialized unknown fonts. Additionally, due to the nature of a logo (as brand identity), there is no guarantee about its context or placement in an image, in reality logos could appear on any product, background or advertising surface. Also, this problem has large intro-class variations e.g. For a specific brand, there exist various logos types (old and new Adidas logos, small and big versions of Nike) and inter-class variations e.g. there exists logos which belong to different brands but look similar (As shown in Figure 1.)

Figure 1. Logo variations exemplar images. Left variations of brands Adidas. Notice, different graphical figure. Right variations of brands Chanel - Gucci, Vodafone, Target, beats, bebo and Pinterest. Notice, similar looking logos but belong to different brands.

Logo Detection using yolov2 on android

YOLO [12] (As shown in Figure 2) is a little bit less precise but it is a really fast detector, this chapter will try to explain how it works and also give a reference working with TensorFlow. The idea of this detector is that you run the image on a CNN model and get the detection on a single pass. First the image is resized to 448x448, then fed to the network and finally the output is filtered by a Non-max suppression algorithm. YOLOv2 is an improved version of YOLOv1 introduced in (Redmon et al. 2016) [13].

Figure 2. The YOLO Detection System.

Network Architecture

The input to the network is 416x416x3 image in YOLOv2-tiny. There is no fully connected layer in it.

Table 1. Details of Network.

Layer	kern el	Stride/Filters	Output shape
Input			416x416x3
Convolution	3×3	16-Jan	416x416x16
MaxPooling	2×2	2	208x208x16
Convolution	3×3	Jan-32	208x208x32
MaxPooling	2×2	2	104x104x32
Convolution	3×3	Jan-64	104x104x64
MaxPooling	2×2	2	52x52x64
Convolution	3×3	1/128	52x52x128
MaxPooling	2×2	2	26x26x128
Convolution	3×3	1/256	26x26x256
MaxPooling	2×2	2	13x13x256
Convolution	3×3	1/512	13x13x512
MaxPooling	2×2	1	13x13x1024
Convolution	3×3	1/1024	13x13x1024
Convolution	3×3	1	13x13x1024
Convolution	1×1	1/175	13x13x175

Dataset

In our project we used FlickrLogos-32 dataset. The FlickrLogos-32 dataset contains photos showing brand logos and is meant for the valuation of multi-class logo recognition as well as logo retrieval methods on real-world images. Logos of 32 different logo classes and 6000 negative images were collected by downloading them from Flickr. The dataset includes images, ground truth, annotations (bounding boxes plus binary masks), evaluation scripts and pre-computed visual features.

Result and training process

Figure 3-4. Detection-results for our project False and True positive.

Show us the result of mean average precision (mAP).

Using this criterium, we can calculate mean average precision object detection (mAP), resulting in a mAP value from 0 to 100% (As shown in Figure 11). Detection exhibits fairly good detection performance, especially on distinctive logos such as that of Huawei with 94%. You only look once (YOLO) is a really fast real-time object detection system. With my TensorFlow model On a NVidia GeForce 1070, it processes in real-time at 30-35 FPS (frames per second) with a mAP

(Mean average precision) of 82% and it can track logos very smoothly. In mobile android phones (Honor 9) we have made the process result as shown in Figure 12 by conducting a series of experiments, the quantitative performance measure of logo detection. Training dark flow and our custom CNN architecture took an immense amount of time. We trained our models in batches of 64 in 8 mini-batches. This allowed us to efficiently train 64 images every step.

Method	Adidas Corona Google Ritt/ huawei	Aldi Dhl Guinness shell	apple erdi/ under omur Hein sing	becks esso Hp Starbucks	Bmw Fedex Milka Stella arतोis	Carls berg Ferrari Nvidia texaco	Chimay Ford Paulaner tsingtao	Cococola Fosters Pepsi ups	mAP
FRCN + AlexNet	47.8	69.1	68.6	71.7	81.7	59.1	70.9	58.8	73.5
	90.9	56.9	83.6	89.4	70.8	88.3	85.7	86	
	90.9	81	66.5	N/A	46.6	52.4	98	42	
	63.3	50.6	83.5	99.3	89.9	81.5	86.7	70.5	
FRCN + VGG	61.6	67.2	84.9	72.5	70	49.6	71.9	33	74.4
	92.9	53.5	80.1	88.8	61.3	90	84.2	49.7	
	85.2	89.4	57.8	N/A	34.6	50.3	98.6	34.2	
	63	57.4	94.2	95.9	82.2	84.4	84.3	81.5	
YOLOv2-Tiny	0.79	0.91	0.78	0.93	0.82	0.85	0.79	0.81	82.5
	0.81	0.77	0.8	0.85	0.77	0.77	0.8	0.83	
	0.92	0.85	N/A	0.81	0.74	0.78	0.83	0.72	
	0.94	0.78	N/A	0.94	0.92	0.87	0.87	0.74	

Table 2. Experimental result of each classes using FlickrLogos-32 and corporation with previous works[15].

Training on a NVidia GeForce 1070, each step took 0.5 seconds. This allowed us to train each model for 2000 epochs, so we can observe the early stopping point and the weights that gave us the best accuracies. YOLO's implementation allowed us to save our weight files every 10000 steps, so we just let it continually train overnight so we can scrap the accuracy in the morning using a script. We have significant results that show our model works better with our dataset above with a little less than 2000 epochs. We trained up to 2000 epochs and the accuracy peaked at epoch 1500. We experimented with running different learning rates our accuracy never got any better.

Figure 12. Shows the logo detection through Honor 9.

Conclusion

I have trained the model on the FlickrLogos-32 dataset and experiment results to show that YOLOv2 performs very well in real-time logo detection. By performing a comprehensive analysis of YOLOv2 over FlickrLogos-32 dataset, we found that the experiment result showed that we managed to achieve a final mean average precision (mAP) 82.53% and 30-35 FPS (frames per second) speed on an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1070 and our models performed well at the detection, with very low false-positive rates possible for a fairly reasonable. The application runs smoothly on the current test hardware. However, the main part of the goal was successfully implemented, a working application that utilizes a neural network model for object detection.

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